

Statue des Wilhelm Tell (Daheim-Park, Zug)

Processing Report
08 July 2022

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	64	Camera stations:	61
Flying altitude:	1.86 m	Tie points:	90,503
Ground resolution:	0.174 mm/pix	Projections:	279,671
Coverage area:	5.87e+03 cm ²	Reprojection error:	0.771 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
Canon EOS 60D, EF50mm f/1....	5184 x 3456	50 mm	4.4 x 4.4 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for Canon EOS 60D, EF50mm f/1.4 USM (50mm).

Canon EOS 60D, EF50mm f/1.4 USM (50mm)

64 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	5184 x 3456	50 mm	4.4 x 4.4 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	K1	K2	K3	P1	P2
F	12330.2	0.41	1.00	0.00	-0.03	-0.16	0.12	-0.09	0.10	-0.01
Cx	45.2505	0.68		1.00	0.02	-0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.87	0.04
Cy	-18.4861	0.58			1.00	0.00	0.02	-0.02	0.01	0.77
K1	-0.165051	0.00069				1.00	-0.96	0.89	0.00	-0.02
K2	0.674947	0.027					1.00	-0.98	-0.01	0.02
K3	-4.58145	0.3						1.00	0.01	-0.01
P1	-0.000244792	1.4e-05							1.00	0.01
P2	-0.000467404	1.2e-05								1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 3. GCP locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated GCP locations are marked with a dot or crossing.

Count	X error (mm)	Y error (mm)	Z error (mm)	XY error (mm)	Total (mm)
4	3.99646	8.57935	0.973117	9.46451	9.5144

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (mm)	Y error (mm)	Z error (mm)	Total (mm)	Image (pix)
vl	-5.49696	1.95023	-1.3185	5.97983	4.494 (5)
vr	-1.54678	-0.812475	0.927938	1.97831	2.815 (10)
hr	1.72316	11.4584	-0.550383	11.6003	7.601 (8)
hl	5.32057	-12.5961	0.94095	13.7061	5.311 (11)
Total	3.99646	8.57935	0.973117	9.5144	5.293

Table 4. Control points.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (mm)	Y error (mm)	Z error (mm)	Total (mm)	Image (pix)
target 278					1.002 (4)
target 279					1.113 (4)
Total					

Table 5. Check points.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Scale Bars

Label	Distance (m)	Error (m)
target 278_target 279	0.250389	0.000388762
Total		0.000388762

Table 6. Control scale bars.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 0.698 mm/pix
Point density: 2.05 points/mm²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	64
Aligned cameras	61
Markers	6
Scale bars	1
Coordinate system	CH1903+ / LV95 (EPSG::2056)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Point Cloud

Points	90,503 of 137,822
RMS reprojection error	0.121062 (0.770836 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.366801 (26.9215 pix)
Mean key point size	6.038 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	2.90503

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	High
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	No
Key point limit	40,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	10,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	No
Matching time	4 minutes 2 seconds
Matching memory usage	800.68 MB
Alignment time	1 minutes 1 seconds
Alignment memory usage	202.02 MB
Date created	2022:03:17 20:16:37
Software version	1.8.2.0
File size	8.58 MB

Depth Maps

Count	61
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	Lowest
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	6 minutes 38 seconds
Memory usage	547.59 MB
Date created	2022:07:07 11:47:19
Software version	1.8.3.14331
File size	5.71 MB

Dense Point Cloud

Points	7,122,384
Point colors	3 bands, uint8

Depth maps generation parameters

Quality	Medium
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16

Processing time	1 hours 48 minutes
Dense cloud generation parameters	
Processing time	2 minutes 55 seconds
Date created	2022:03:17 22:12:11
Software version	1.8.2.0
File size	93.70 MB
Model	
Faces	618,203
Vertices	309,709
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	8,192 x 8,192, 4 bands, uint8
Depth maps generation parameters	
Quality	Medium
Filtering mode	Mild
Max neighbors	16
Processing time	1 hours 48 minutes
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Arbitrary
Source data	Depth maps
Interpolation	Enabled
Strict volumetric masks	No
Processing time	3 minutes 20 seconds
Memory usage	1.68 GB
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	8,192
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	1 minutes 53 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	494.71 MB
Blending time	8 minutes 24 seconds
Blending memory usage	6.15 GB
Date created	2022:04:08 13:33:13
Software version	1.8.2.0
File size	124.10 MB
DEM	
Size	1,919 x 1,528
Coordinate system	CH1903+ / LV95 (EPSG::2056)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	2 seconds
Memory usage	142.27 MB
Date created	2022:07:08 11:03:39
Software version	1.8.3.14331
File size	3.37 MB
Orthomosaic	
Size	5,715 x 5,315
Coordinate system	CH1903+ / LV95 (EPSG::2056)
Colors	3 bands, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Blending mode	Mosaic
Surface	DEM
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	No

Processing time	1 minutes 6 seconds
Memory usage	1.64 GB
Date created	2022:07:08 11:00:23
Software version	1.8.3.14331
File size	266.76 MB

System

Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	1.8.3 build 14331
OS	Linux 64 bit
RAM	3.83 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-8265U CPU @ 1.60GHz
GPU(s)	None